

ANALYSIS OF MUUN UMKM MARKETING STRATEGY IN INCREASING BUYING INTEREST AND CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

Dwi Sagita¹, Nurul Alya Abdi², Muhammad Faris Al-Muzaki³, Egi Utami Jailani⁴, Rusydi Abubakar⁵

Universitas Malikussaleh, Lhokseumawe

Email: rusydiabubakar@unimal.ac.id

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Abstract

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) play a strategic role in Indonesia's economy, particularly in the culinary sector, which continues to grow rapidly. This study aims to analyze the marketing strategies implemented by MUUN Donuts in increasing purchase intention and customer satisfaction. The analysis focuses on the application of the marketing mix (4P: Product, Price, Place, Promotion), Segmenting, Targeting, and Positioning (STP) strategies, the role of customer relationship management through promotional programs, and the obstacles faced in implementing these strategies. This research employs a descriptive qualitative approach, with data collected through observation, interviews, and documentation. The results indicate that MUUN Donuts has implemented its marketing strategies effectively by emphasizing product quality, competitive pricing, strategic location, and digital promotion through social media. The STP strategy targeting young consumers, students, and families is considered effective in reaching the intended market segments. Furthermore, customer relationship strategies through promotions and digital interactions have a positive impact on purchase decisions and customer loyalty. However, MUUN Donuts faces several challenges, including fluctuations in raw material prices and declining sales during academic holiday periods. Therefore, adaptive and innovative marketing strategies are needed to maintain competitiveness and ensure business sustainability.

Keywords: MSMEs, marketing strategy, marketing mix (4P), STP, customer relationship, purchase intention.

INTRODUCTION

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) play a strategic role in driving Indonesia's economic growth, both as drivers of local economic activity and as job providers. Among the various MSME sectors, the culinary sector has shown particularly rapid growth in line with changing lifestyles, leading to an increasingly consumerist and open mind towards innovation in food and beverage products. The high public interest in culinary products has made this sector one of the business sectors with quite intense competition, requiring MSMEs to be able to implement appropriate marketing strategies to survive and grow sustainably. In facing such competition, marketing strategy is a crucial factor in determining the success of a business. Marketing not only serves as a means to introduce products to consumers, but also plays a role in creating value, building brand image, and increasing customer satisfaction and loyalty. One widely used marketing strategy framework is the 4Ps marketing mix, which includes product, price, place, and promotion. These four elements are interrelated and must be managed in an integrated manner to create a competitive advantage. Furthermore, a Segmenting, Targeting, and Positioning (STP) strategy is also necessary to ensure that the products offered match the characteristics and needs of the target market. With the advancement of digital technology, customer relationship management has become a crucial aspect of MSME marketing strategies. Utilizing social media and digital promotions allows businesses to establish two-way interactions with consumers more effectively, quickly, and personally. For young consumers, particularly Generation Z, digital promotions, attractive product visuals, and promotional programs such as discounts and bundling are significant factors in influencing purchasing decisions. Therefore, integrating the 4Ps, STP, and customer relationship strategies is crucial in increasing purchasing interest and customer satisfaction. MUUN Donuts is a local culinary MSME specializing in sweet treats and targeting the younger generation. This business offers contemporary donuts with an aesthetic appearance, a variety of trendy flavors, and

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relatively affordable prices. Despite showing quite positive developments, MUUN Donuts still faces various challenges, such as competition from large-scale donut brands, fluctuating raw material prices, and a decline in customer numbers during certain periods, especially during academic holidays. These conditions require an evaluation of the marketing strategy that has been implemented so that the business can maintain competitiveness and customer loyalty. On the other hand, academic studies specifically discussing the implementation of integrated marketing strategies, including the 4P marketing mix, STP strategy, and customer relationships in local culinary MSMEs are still relatively limited. Some studies tend to focus on certain aspects separately, thus not providing a comprehensive picture of the effectiveness of the overall marketing strategy. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the marketing strategy implemented by the MUUN Donuts MSME, with an emphasis on the implementation of the 4P marketing mix, STP strategy, and the role of customer relationships through promotional programs in influencing purchasing decisions and customer satisfaction. The results of this study are expected to provide practical contributions for MSMEs, especially in the culinary sector, as a consideration in designing marketing strategies that are more effective, adaptive to market changes, and oriented towards business sustainability.

Research purposes

This study aims to analyze and evaluate the marketing strategies implemented by the MUUN MSME, with a focus on the implementation of the 4P marketing mix, Segmenting, Targeting, and Positioning (STP) strategy, and efforts to build relationships with customers through promotional programs. Furthermore, this study also aims to identify various obstacles faced in implementing these marketing strategies. The results of this study are expected to provide a comprehensive overview of the effectiveness of the MUUN MSME marketing strategy and serve as a reference for other culinary MSMEs in designing more effective and sustainable marketing strategies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Social Media Marketing

Social media marketing is a subset of digital marketing that utilizes social media platforms to create value, build relationships, and enhance interactions between companies and customers through relevant content and active user participation (Tuten & Solomon, 2017). Social media enables more intensive two-way communication, allowing companies to not only deliver marketing messages but also receive direct feedback from consumers. Kotler and Keller (2016) state that social media marketing is a marketing strategy that utilizes online communities, social networks, blogs, and forums to reach consumers, create interactions, and increase brand awareness and sales. In this context, social media functions as a marketing communication tool that can strengthen the emotional connection between brands and consumers. Kietzmann et al. (2011) explain that the effectiveness of social media marketing can be analyzed using a honeycomb framework that encompasses seven main elements: identity, interaction, distribution, existence, connection, image, and community. This framework demonstrates that social media serves not only as a promotional tool but also as a space for building community, strengthening brand identity, and creating ongoing engagement with consumers. In practice, social media marketing utilizes various platforms such as Instagram, TikTok, Facebook, YouTube, and X to promote products and services. The use of visual content, short videos, and trend-based interactions makes social media an effective tool for increasing brand awareness and reaching a wider consumer base, particularly among the younger generation. Therefore, social media marketing is a relevant strategy for MSMEs facing increasingly competitive markets.

Social Media Content Marketing

Content marketing is a strategic marketing approach focused on creating and distributing relevant, valuable, and consistent content to attract and retain the attention of a specific audience, with the goal of driving profitable consumer action (Pulizzi, 2014). Content serves not only as a promotional tool but also as a means of communication that can provide information, education, and entertainment to consumers. Kumar et al. (2016) emphasize that content marketing plays a crucial role in creating customer interaction and engagement, which can ultimately influence loyalty and purchasing decisions. This aligns with Du Plessis's (2017) view that content is a strategic communication tool for brands to build long-term relationships with audiences through the delivery of consistent and useful information. Baltes (2015) added that content marketing is a marketing approach that utilizes creative content to increase brand awareness and generate positive consumer responses. In the context of social media, content such as educational videos, infographics,

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tutorials, and product information are effective tools for building consumer trust. Therefore, social media content marketing plays a crucial role in creating long-term relationships between brands and customers.

Influencer Marketing

Influencer marketing is a marketing strategy that utilizes individuals or figures with influence and trust in online communities to influence consumer attitudes and purchasing decisions through recommendations, testimonials, or personal experiences (Kotler et al., 2017). Boerman (2020) states that influencer marketing is a form of endorsement-based advertising conducted through social media to influence consumer perceptions and behavior. The advantage of influencer marketing lies in its high level of trust and engagement, as influencers are often viewed as credible and authentic sources of information by their followers (Lou & Yuan, 2019). Personal and authentic influencer content has been shown to significantly influence consumer purchase intentions, especially when presented in the form of reviews or firsthand experiences (Ki et al., 2020). For MSMEs, influencer marketing is a relatively effective and efficient strategy because it allows businesses with limited resources to reach a more specific target market through personal influencer recommendations. Djafarova and Trofimenko (2019) stated that the use of micro-influencers can be a strategic alternative for MSMEs due to their greater proximity to the audience and lower costs compared to macro-influencers. Therefore, influencer marketing plays a crucial role in increasing consumer trust and strengthening the brand image of MSMEs.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study employed a qualitative approach with descriptive methods. This approach was chosen because the study aimed to understand and describe in-depth the marketing strategies implemented by the MUUN Donuts MSME to increase purchasing interest and customer satisfaction. The descriptive method was used to provide a systematic overview of the implementation of the 4P marketing mix, Segmenting, Targeting, and Positioning (STP) strategy, and the role of customer relationships through promotional programs without conducting statistical hypothesis testing. The research object in this study is MUUN Donuts, a culinary business located in Lhokseumawe City. The selection of the research object is based on the consideration that MUUN Donuts is a local MSME that actively implements modern marketing strategies, particularly through social media, and targets the younger generation. This research was conducted in 2025 with a focus on the marketing activities carried out by MUUN Donuts in its daily operations. The data sources in this study consist of primary and secondary data. Primary data were obtained directly through interviews with the owner and employees of MUUN Donuts to obtain information regarding marketing strategies, promotional programs, and obstacles encountered in their implementation. In addition, direct observations were conducted to observe the condition of the business location, products offered, prices, and promotional activities carried out. Secondary data were obtained from various supporting sources, such as business documents, MUUN Donuts' social media, and relevant literature in the form of books, scientific journals, and articles related to MSME marketing strategies. The data collection techniques used in this study included interviews, observation, and documentation. The interviews were conducted in a semi-structured manner to obtain in-depth yet focused data. Observations involved directly observing marketing activities and interactions between business owners and consumers. Documentation was used to supplement the data, including product photos, digital promotional content, and written information related to MUUN Donuts' marketing activities. The data analysis technique used was qualitative descriptive analysis. The collected data were analyzed through the stages of data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. The analysis was conducted by linking field findings with the 4P marketing mix concept, STP strategy, and customer relationships to obtain a comprehensive picture of the effectiveness of the marketing strategy implemented by the MUUN Donuts MSME.

RESEARCH RESULT

The research results show that MUUN Donuts MSME has implemented a fairly structured marketing strategy through the 4P marketing mix (Product, Price, Place, Promotion), Segmenting, Targeting, and Positioning (STP) strategy, and customer relationship management through promotional programs. The implementation of these strategies has made a positive contribution to increasing purchasing interest and customer satisfaction, although several obstacles remain that need to be optimized. From a **product perspective**, MUUN Donuts offers contemporary donuts with a variety of flavors, aesthetic appeal, and relatively good quality ingredients. The innovative flavors and attractive product visuals are key draws, especially for younger consumers who are sensitive to culinary and aesthetic trends. These findings align with modern marketing concepts that emphasize the importance of emotional value and consumer experience, where products

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are judged not only by their function but also by their appearance and suitability to consumers' lifestyles. However, the study also found differences in consumer preferences for sweetness levels and the amount of cream filling, indicating the need for product adjustments to reach a wider market segment. In terms of **price**, MUUN Donuts sets competitive prices that are balanced with the quality of the products offered. Relatively affordable prices for students create a good perception of value (value for money) in the eyes of consumers. This pricing strategy has proven to be able to attract consumers to make repeat purchases. However, fluctuations in raw material prices pose a challenge because they directly impact production costs and pricing policies. MUUN Donuts chooses to maintain product quality despite having to make gradual price adjustments, which in the long run can strengthen consumer trust in the brand. In terms of **location**, MUUN Donuts' strategic and easily accessible location provides a distinct advantage in attracting customers. In addition to direct sales at the outlet, the use of online delivery platforms expands market reach and facilitates consumer purchasing. This combination of offline and online distribution channels demonstrates MUUN Donuts' adaptation to changing consumer behavior, which increasingly relies on digital services.

Furthermore, in terms of **promotion**, MUUN Donuts relies on social media as its primary means of promotion. Engaging visual content, collaborations with local influencers, and promotional programs at specific times have proven effective in increasing brand awareness and consumer purchasing interest. Digital promotions also enable two-way interaction between MSMEs and customers, strengthening emotional bonds and trust in the brand. However, reliance on the student segment has led to a decline in sales during academic holidays, indicating the need for market diversification. **the Segmenting, Targeting, and Positioning (STP)** analysis show that MUUN Donuts has a fairly clear target market. Segmentation is focused on young consumers, students, and families who enjoy sweet snacks. Targeting is directed at consumer groups who actively use social media and have a high tendency to consume contemporary products. Meanwhile, MUUN Donuts' positioning is built as a contemporary donut brand with premium quality but remains affordable. This positioning is the main differentiator of MUUN Donuts compared to other local competitors. From a **customer relationship perspective**, promotional programs such as discounts, bundling, and seasonal promotions play a significant role in influencing purchasing decisions. Consumers perceive added value, encouraging repeat purchases. This strategy also contributes to building customer loyalty, especially when supported by consistent product quality and excellent service. Active engagement through social media further strengthens the relationship between MUUN Donuts and its customers. Overall, the research results indicate that the marketing strategy implemented by MUUN Donuts has been quite effective in increasing purchasing interest and customer satisfaction. However, strategy optimization is still needed, especially in dealing with seasonal demand fluctuations and expanding market segments to reduce dependence on student consumers. The continuous integration of the 4Ps, STP, and customer relationship strategies is expected to increase the competitiveness and sustainability of MUUN Donuts' MSME amidst the increasingly competitive culinary industry.

Discussion

The application of the 4P marketing mix at MUUN Donuts MSME shows that product strategy is the most dominant element in attracting consumer attention. Flavor innovation, product variety, and attractive visual appearance strengthen the product's value in the eyes of consumers. This is in line with modern marketing concepts that emphasize value creation and customer experience as key factors in building long-term relationships between companies and consumers. Products are not only seen as fulfilling functional needs, but also as part of the lifestyle and expression of consumer identity, especially in the younger generation segment. From a pricing perspective, pricing tailored to the purchasing power of the target market reflects a *value-based pricing strategy*. Prices perceived as commensurate with product quality contribute to positive consumer perceptions and encourage repeat purchases. However, in the context of MSMEs, fluctuating raw material prices pose a challenge that can impact price stability and profit margins. This situation demonstrates the need for a more flexible and adaptive pricing strategy to maintain a balance between product quality and business sustainability. In terms of distribution, the integration of direct sales and digital platforms reflects an adaptation to changing consumer behavior that prioritizes ease and speed of access. A distribution strategy that combines offline and online channels aligns with modern marketing concepts focused on customer convenience. This approach enables MSMEs to expand their market reach without significantly increasing operational costs. The promotional aspect demonstrates the crucial role of digital marketing in increasing brand visibility and building engagement with consumers. Social media enables more personalized and interactive two-way communication, strengthening the emotional connection between brands and customers. Visual content and trend-based promotions are effective tools for capturing

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audience attention, especially among consumers active on social media. This supports digital marketing theory, which emphasizes the importance of engagement as an indicator of promotional success. The implemented Segmenting, Targeting, and Positioning (STP) strategy focuses on the younger generation, characterized by a consumerist lifestyle and an interest in contemporary products. Segmentation based on age and behavior allows for more relevant marketing messaging. Targeting active social media consumers strengthens the effectiveness of the digital marketing strategy, while positioning as a trendy, affordable donut brand is a key differentiator compared to competitors. However, dependence on a single market segment poses the risk of declining demand over time, making segment diversification a strategy worth considering.

The implementation of social media marketing, content marketing, and influencer marketing contributes to building consumer trust and engagement. Informative, consistent, and relevant content plays a role in building long-term relationships with audiences, while influencer marketing strengthens brand credibility through personalized and authentic recommendations. These findings align with the theory that the level of trust in information sources has a significant influence on consumer purchase intentions. In the context of customer relationships, promotional programs such as discounts and bundling serve as a form of appreciation for consumers and foster loyalty. This strategy demonstrates that long-term relationships with customers are built not only through product quality but also through positive experiences and a sense of appreciation. However, limited human resources in digital marketing management can impact the consistency of implemented strategies, necessitating more structured management. Overall, this discussion demonstrates that integrating the 4Ps marketing mix, STP strategy, and digital marketing is a relevant approach for MSMEs to increase competitiveness. Optimizing strategies, particularly in market segment diversification and sustainable digital marketing management, is crucial for MSMEs to survive and thrive in the increasingly competitive culinary industry.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results and discussion, it can be concluded that the MUUN Donuts MSME has implemented a marketing strategy that includes the 4P marketing mix, Segmenting, Targeting, and Positioning (STP) strategy, and digital marketing through social media, content marketing, and influencer marketing. The implementation of this strategy has generally been quite effective in increasing purchasing interest, interaction, and consumer satisfaction, particularly among the younger generation. A product strategy emphasizing innovation, variety, and attractive visuals is a key factor in creating value for consumers. Relatively affordable pricing aligned with the purchasing power of the target market also strengthens the product's perceived value. Utilizing offline and online distribution channels demonstrates adaptability to changing consumer behavior, while digital promotion through social media plays a key role in increasing brand visibility and customer engagement. The STP strategy implemented demonstrates a clear focus on the social media-active consumer segment, positioning itself as a trendy, high-quality yet affordable donut brand. Furthermore, efforts to build relationships with customers through promotional programs and collaborations with influencers have been shown to contribute to increasing consumer trust and loyalty. However, this study also identified several challenges, such as limited human resources for digital marketing management, fluctuating raw material prices, and dependence on specific market segments.

Suggestion

Based on these conclusions, several recommendations can be made as follows. First, the MUUN Donuts MSME is advised to continue product innovation, both in terms of flavor, size, and menu variety, to reach a wider consumer segment and reduce dependence on a single market group. Second, a more adaptive pricing strategy is needed to address fluctuations in production costs, for example through portion control, raw material efficiency, or gradual price adjustments. Third, MUUN Donuts is advised to strengthen its digital marketing strategy with more structured and consistent content planning, as well as increasing the use of interactive social media features to strengthen consumer engagement. Collaboration with influencers, especially *micro-influencers*, can be further developed as it is considered effective and efficient for MSMEs. Fourth, in the long term, MUUN Donuts MSME needs to consider diversifying its market segments, such as targeting family or working consumers, to ensure stable demand is maintained over time. For further research, it is recommended to use a quantitative or mixed methods approach to more measurably measure the influence of marketing strategies on variables such as purchase intention, loyalty, and customer satisfaction. Further research could also expand the research to other culinary MSMEs to obtain more comprehensive results and broader generalizations.

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